

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Minimal Metadata Elements - Virtual
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators:
- Note-Taker: Amelia Pilgrim
- Chat monitor: Fred Kepner

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Minimal Metadata Elements - *Rebecca Ringuette*

Pre-Activity

- Miro board is set up splitting Mission Data + Research Data

Speaker/Lightning Talk Notes

- Mandatory Metadata
 - Comments:
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- Recommended Metadata
 - Attempts to support how users already want to search. Connecting users of data sets to things that help them understand how to use such data sets
- Optional Metadata
- For spatial bounds – this is for data sets, not mission/flight path
- Questions about Data Site
 - Publication year is mandatory from Data Site
 - Creators can be teams of individuals. Data Site already supports this
 - Data Site creates citation based on the metadata you give it
 - DOI and landing page URLs are separate - communicate landing page to Data Site to update connection

Webex Chat Comments

- Couple random questions:
 - 1. Is this metadata that would necessarily be in each individual data file?
 - These are the metadata requirements a researcher would have to fill out before it is submitted. This is out of scope, but Ideally the DOI would go
 - 2. Is your intent eventually to specify what keyword or attribute name each piece of metadata goes into?
 - Oh please no. This is meant to satisfy requirements, particularly on the mandatory piece, and second, give us info on the correct data governance for these things. Is this funded by NASA or not? This helps us determine prioritization. These help us to determine how long we should keep this. Is it is a 100tb data sample, we will not put that on the cloud but send it through the proper channels
 - What is a legacy data set?
 - There are thousands of data sets that we are trying to connect DOIs to. If we connect them to missions they come from, that secondary connection through the DOIs would make the process much easier.
 - Legacy set = more than 5-10 years ago
 - Does Zenodo come under this?
 - Don't feel I have time to summarize here, but it would be on the research side - Not mission side
 - Finding a funding award number should not be optional
 - "Can you elaborate"

Q&A

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